

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ogundipe**FIRST NAME:** Akinwale**PROGRAM CODE:** DME**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 01**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing an Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 2-9)
2. Structuring your Ideas (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 2-3)
3. Referencing the Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 3)
4. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 3-4)
5. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 4)

WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing has never been my strong point; in the past, I have written enough to allow me to pass my dissertations. While not understanding the basis and techniques. This personal fear, as not real, makes academic writing of interest to me. The decision to embark on a Ph.D. studies program will help me develop the skills and techniques to enable me to write confidently, not just because it is necessary.

Starting my Ph.D. study with the ACA-401D course has given me a sign of happiness because some of these issues and topics that look so difficult have been explained in simple terms. The video and videos explaining how to put citations and reference my academic writing have been beneficial for me. I now understand better how to use Zotero to arrange and source materials for my writing and referencing and how to update citations for PDF materials used for my writing.

The chapter clearly explains the importance of planning and taking time to structure one's ideas and thoughts. How do you use paragraphs and write in simple English while focusing on the topic and objectives of the research? It also discusses the value of getting

others to review our ideas and findings and discuss them to help ensure our writing meets the expected standard.

While all the topics discussed in the chapter have been very informative and very useful, I will discuss my learning below using five topics: writing an academic essay, structuring your ideas, referencing the essay, some rules of thumb for writing, and plagiarism.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

The course pack has proven interesting; before now, I did not consider technical reports from program implementation to be academic writing. It defines academic writing as nonfictional writing with structure, citations, and references, with the aim to test hypotheses and communicate findings to provide evidence for the tested ideas (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

Like every other piece of writing, academic writing requires planning, researching the topic, and, most importantly, putting one's thoughts and findings down in writing. I have always struggled to kick-start my writing, whether it is a report, personal letter or any writing. This has always made writing a massive challenge for me, and the more I delay, the more stressful and difficult it gets. Reading the course pack, I learned that starting my writing is the first key element of academic writing. I must give myself enough time to read more about my topic, plan, and write (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

In planning my writing, I need to put down my initial ideas, define my questions, and identify the kind of analysis I will do. This will help to guide my research work and ensure that it is within the scope of my research. It will ensure that I can answer the research questions and detail the type of information to use (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

Researching my topic helps me gain more insight into the subject matter and see what has been written and discussed. It also helps me identify key research limitations and gaps, which can help me refocus on my topic. While researching my research topic, it is essential to know what is crucial for me to read, defining if the material is useful for my proposed topic and if it will be helpful in my research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 8).

3) STRUCTURING YOUR IDEAS

Another key step in planning my writing is to develop a structure that will help ensure I can get the best answers for my research questions. I then will list the information needed to answer these questions, with appropriate examples that can help drive home such an idea or argument. While these answers and information could be very many, considering the number of materials being reviewed for the research, I must select and map out the most relevant answers to my question research questions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9-10).

Structuring one idea by mapping relevant information answers and selecting the best-fit answers for the essay may be a considerable task. However, it increases the chances of a successful essay. This is good learning for me, considering I want to jump right into writing without taking time to structure my writing.

4) REFERENCING THE ESSAY

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 11), “all academic essays MUST contain references”. This differentiates academic writing from other kinds of writing. I have also come to appreciate that it is not enough to reference my work, but more importantly, I must ensure that I use the appropriate reference for the report or journal. Each university and journal publication has its preferred referencing style, which should be followed strictly. Others, such as EUCLID University, will consistently accept any referencing format throughout the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11).

I understand that not referencing my research writing using the appropriate referencing style is considered plagiarism, which is a serious academic offense (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). It is my responsibility to ensure that I review the necessary guidance to understand the appropriate referencing style for my academic writing.

5) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING

Academic writing requires some techniques which can be perfected over time. These techniques can be learned by following and sticking to basic rules. It is essential to state clearly in the opening paragraph of the academic paper what the paper is most. This way, the reader would know what the paper is about. It also helps to guide one’s thoughts as the writing progresses.

I understand that it is my responsibility to ensure that I am focused while trying to build up my arguments or ideas. The relevant aspects of the theory my work will address should be clearly stated. Efforts should be made to ensure that my evidence and statements are not supported by examples that are not in line with the theory or ideas I am trying to explain. It is essential to stay within the scope of my ideas, avoiding distractions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13).

Writing in clear and straightforward English is also essential for academic writing. I now understand that my writing will not be judged soundly because I use a high vocabulary or write lengthy paragraphs. Instead, I should use words that will help my readers to be carried along and clearly understand what is being communicated. Reducing the ideas discussed per paragraph will help ensure sizeable lines per paragraph.

My readers cannot assume or stand under my viewpoints beyond what I have written; as such, it is very important that I take my discussions and writing more seriously. To do this, I must critique my work, asking myself what the view of the reader or the person

will be whose theory or concept I am evaluating. Getting the opinions of others, particularly academic writers and colleagues, as their input can be used to refine the paper. Lastly, it is crucial that one read through multiple times to ensure the flow of the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14).

6) PLAGIARISM

I will be guilty of plagiarism, where I have used word-for-word texts and sentences from any of the materials, I have reviewed to support my writing. To avoid this, I must ensure the words are in quotation marks, indicating that they are direct words used in the reviewed text, either in a journal, book, or other sources. Where I have paraphrased (which is most advisable), I must ensure that I cite the sources using a footnote or a citation using the appropriate style. Anything short of this will be considered plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14).

I understand that if I am found to have plagiarized in any form in my academic writing, the penalty could be a lower grade. In more severe cases, I could be giving a failing grade for the course (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14).

7) CONCLUSION

This chapter provided an overview of academic writing, explaining the concept, detailing key steps, and providing a guide for planning and conducting such writing. It stresses the importance of structuring and referencing using the appropriate referencing styles to meet the needs of the journal or the university.

While some of the issues discussed in the chapter are not new, I have better understood the concepts and learned some new ideas. My key learning is the importance of starting my writing without wasting time. This again stresses to me the importance of fighting procrastination. This is a good start to my learning and has given me the confidence to write.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.